

**METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE APPLICATION OF DEFINITE INTEGRAL
TO GEOMETRICAL PROBLEMS**

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Annotation. In this article, the science that is currently of greatest importance is the science of mathematics. In recent years, mathematics is the most relevant subject. On this basis, learning mathematics is becoming more difficult. For this reason, the number of classes in schools and academic lyceums has increased, especially in mathematics. For this reason, the elementary part of mathematics, the science of mathematical analysis, algebra and number theory, along with geometry, are taught in higher educational institutions. In this article, we can see mathematical analysis and geometry in a common topic. At the moment, it should be said that concepts such as curve, surface, and volume are fully explained in geometry courses, and we have given them only in the places necessary for the course of mathematical analysis. This article focuses mainly on Let's look at the method of passing this topic between two subjects in the same order.

Key words: Integral, surface, volume, geometric shapes, mathematics and curve .

Enter. The word method is a Greek word that means "to show the way." The concept of "educational method" is one of the main concepts in modern methodology and didactics, but until recently, this concept was used in various methodological literature in different contexts. In methodological literature up to the 19th century, the concept of "method" is used as a description of the topic that describes the main content of the mathematics course. For example, "Method of learning numbers", "Method of learning geometric figures", etc.

Main part:

D be a flat figure (sphere) bounded by a closed line in the plane .

M be the polygon inscribed in this figure, and M' be the polygon inscribed outside this figure. We denote their surfaces as σ and σ' , respectively. Obviously, there are infinitely many such polygons. An arbitrary polygon M is a subset of $M' \supset D$ such that $M \subset D$. If we look at a polygon M' and its surface σ' , then for all $M \subset D$ polygons, the set of faces $\{\sigma\}$ is bounded from above by this fixed number σ' . Hence, the set of numbers $\{\sigma\}$ has an exact upper bound and

$$\sup_{M \subset D} \sigma \leq \sigma'$$

A similar M' and σ' , the set of numbers $\{\sigma'\}$ is bounded below, assuming that

$$\inf_{M' \supset D} \sigma' \geq \sigma$$

the inequality becomes relevant.

If $\sup \sigma = S$ and $\inf \sigma' = \underline{S}$. If we introduce symbols S , for arbitrary M , σ and M' , σ' 's

$$\sigma \leq \bar{S} \leq \underline{S} \leq \sigma' \tag{17}$$

relationships will be appropriate.

Description . If for the given figure D $\bar{S} = \underline{S}$, then the figure D is said to have a surface or to be quadrature, and its surface is exactly this

$$S = \bar{S} = \underline{S}$$

is assumed to be equal to the number.

Example : If the figure D itself is a polygon, it is obvious that $\bar{S} = \underline{S}$.

Theorem . D is arbitrary for the plane figure to be quadrature $\epsilon > 0$, there exist such $M(I \subset D)$ and $M'(I' \supset D)$ and for their faces

$$\sigma' - \sigma < \epsilon$$

is necessary and sufficient.

Proof. Necessity . $S = \bar{S} = \underline{S}$ let it be Using the definitions of upper and lower bounds, $\frac{\epsilon}{2}$

such that for M, σ , and M', σ' 's are found that for them $\sigma > S - \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$, $\sigma > S + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ inequalities will be valid. From this

$$\sigma' - \sigma < \frac{\varepsilon}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

originates.

Sufficiency . Now for $\varepsilon > 0$ such that M, σ , and M', σ' are available,

$$\sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$$

be appropriate. Then according to (17).

$$\overline{S} - \underline{S} \leq \sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$$

will be, in which $\overline{S}$ and $\underline{S}$ are fixed numbers. Considering that $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrary, $\overline{S} = \underline{S}$ it follows that the equality holds.

Theorem . If D is a closed and bounded field, then is closed and squared D_1 and D_2 is divided into spheres and they have no common interior points, then the sphere D is also quadrature, and its face S is D_1 and D_2 of sectors S_1 and S_2 is equal to the sum of faces.

Proof. $M_1 \subset D_1$, $M_2 \subset D_2$ and let the areas of these polygons be σ_1 and σ_2 respectively σ . Also, let $M_1 \supset D_1$, $M_2 \supset D_2$ and their faces be σ_1' and σ_2' , respectively .

$$M = M_1 \cup M_2, M' = M'_1 \cup M'_2$$

creating two new polygons and their surfaces σ and σ' as Ravshanki,

$$\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 = \sigma \leq \sigma' = \sigma_1' + \sigma_2'.$$

Arbitrary according to the theorem $\varepsilon > 0$ has such M_1, M'_1 and M_2, M'_2 polygons such that for their surfaces

$$\sigma'_1 - \sigma_1 < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad \sigma'_2 - \sigma_2 < \frac{\varepsilon}{2}$$

inequalities will be valid. From this

$$(\sigma_1' + \sigma_2') - (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) < \varepsilon,$$

Let $\sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$ originate.

Hence, such $M \subset D$ and $M' \supset D$ are found that for their surfaces $\sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$ will be. According to the theorem, it follows that D is a squared field.

Now we find the surface of D . The following

$$\sigma_1 \leq S_1 \leq \sigma'_1, \sigma_2 \leq S_2 \leq \sigma'_2$$

from relationships

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2 \leq S_1 + S_2 \leq \sigma'_1 + \sigma'_2 = \sigma'$$

originates. From this

$$\sigma \leq S \leq \sigma', \quad \sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$$

assuming that

$$|(S_1 + S_2) - S| < \sigma' - \sigma < \varepsilon$$

we get an inequality. ε since the number is arbitrary

$$S = S_1 + S_2$$

equality is appropriate.

The theorem proved above states **the surface additivity property** and is called the surface additivity theorem.

Let us assume that a flat figure D bounded by the straight lines $x=a, x=b, y=0$ and the graph of a nonnegative continuous function $y=f(x)$ is given. We calculate the surface area of this figure. For this, $[a;b]$ is any τ_n of the section we get the division:

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_n = b.$$

m_k and M_k be the smallest and largest values of $f(x)$ on the section $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$, respectively. Corresponding to each $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$ the base consists of this section, and the heights $y=m_k$ and $y=M_k$ Let's make two rectangles.

A polygon consisting of all the smaller rectangles (heights m_k) is a polygon drawn inside D figure, and a polygon consisting of large rectangles is drawn outside. Their surfaces are respectively

$$\sigma = \sum_{k=1}^n m_k \Delta x_k = \underline{S}(\tau_n), \sigma' = \sum_{k=1}^n M_k \Delta x_k = \overline{S}(\tau_n),$$

will be By condition, the function $f(x)$ is continuous, from which it follows that it is integrable. So,

$$\sup \sigma = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \underline{S}(\tau_n) = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \overline{S}(\tau_n) = \inf \sigma' \quad (\lambda = \max_{1 \leq k \leq n} \Delta x_k),$$

i.e. the figure D (curved trapezoid) is squared and its surface

$$S = \int_a^b f(x) dx$$

will be

If the figure D above is bounded by a line $\varphi(x)$ instead of the straight line $y = \varphi(x)$ ($\varphi(x) \leq f(x), x \in [a; b]$) $y=0$ below, and the function is continuous, then

$$S = \int_a^b (f(x) - \varphi(x)) dx$$

will be

An example . $y=x^2$ and $x=y^2$ find the face of the figure bounded by the lines.

Solving . The given figure is from above $y = \sqrt{x}, 0 \leq x \leq 1$ with a line, and from below $y=x^2, 0 \leq x \leq 1$ bounded by a line.

that is why

$$S = \int_0^1 (\sqrt{x} - x^2) dx = \frac{2x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3} \Big|_0^1 - \frac{1}{3} x^3 \Big|_0^1 = \frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

The curve in the curved trapezoid is a parametric method

$\begin{cases} x = \varphi(t), \\ y = \psi(t) \end{cases} (\alpha \leq t \leq \beta)$ is given, in which $\varphi(\alpha) = a, \varphi(\beta) = b, [\alpha; \beta]$ we assume that (t

) is continuous in the section ψ , and $\varphi(t)$ has a monotone and continuous derivative $\varphi'(t)$. Based on the variable substitution rule, we get:

$$S = \int_a^b f(x)dx = \int_\alpha^\beta \Psi(t)\varphi'(t)dt \quad (18)$$

An example . $\begin{cases} x = a \cos t, \\ y = b \sin t \end{cases} 0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$ calculate the face of the ellipse.

Solving . First we find the face of the quarter ellipse:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{S}{4} &= \int_{\frac{\pi}{2}}^0 b \sin t (-a \sin t) dt = ab \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin^2 t dt = \frac{ab}{2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} (1 - \cos 2t) dt = \\ &= \frac{ab}{2} \left(t - \frac{\sin 2t}{2} \right) \Big|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} = \frac{\pi ab}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $S = \pi ab$.

An example . Calculate the face of the figure bounded by the axis of the Ox is and one arc of the cycloid. $\begin{cases} x = a(t - \sin t), \\ y = a(1 - \cos t), \end{cases} 0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$

Solving . (18) according to the formula

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \int_0^{2\pi} a(1 - \cos t)a(1 - \cos t) dt = a^2 \int_0^{2\pi} (1 - \cos t)^2 dt = \\ &= a^2 \left(\int_0^{2\pi} dt - 2 \int_0^{2\pi} \cos t dt + \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^2 t dt \right) = \\ &= a^2 \left((t - 2 \sin t) \Big|_0^{2\pi} + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} (1 + \cos 2t) dt \right) = \\ &= a^2 \left(2\pi + \frac{1}{2} \left(t + \frac{1}{2} \sin 2t \right) \Big|_0^{2\pi} \right) = 3\pi a^2. \end{aligned}$$

It is required to calculate the surface of the figure bounded by rays and the equation $\varphi = \beta$ of the curve $\varphi = \alpha l$ in the polar coordinate system $.r = r(\varphi)$

This figure is a straight figure, that is, a ray with its origin ($\alpha \leq \varphi \leq \beta$) at point $\varphi = \varphi * O r = r(\varphi)$ we assume that it crosses the line in at most one point. We also $r = r(\varphi)$ treat the function as continuous at $[\alpha; \beta]$

with a curve OAB , we use an algorithm consisting of making an integral sum, and then passing to the limit.

1. We divide $[\alpha; \beta]$ into n sections and $\alpha = \varphi_0 < \varphi_1 < \dots < \varphi_n = \beta, \Delta\varphi_k = \varphi_k - \varphi_{k-1}, k = \overline{1, n}$ enter notation. Then the curved sector OAB is divided into n curved sectors.

2. Each $[\varphi_{k-1}; \varphi_k]$, $k = \overline{1, n}$ part is arbitrarily θ_k from the section we select a point and calculate the values of the function $r(\varphi)$ at these points:

$$r_k = r(\theta_k), \quad k = \overline{1, n}$$

3. The function to be invariant and $r_k = r(\theta_k)$ equal to the value of in each $[\varphi_{k-1}; \varphi_k]$ section section . $r = r(\varphi)$ In this case, the radius of the curved part of the sector is $r_k = r(\theta_k)$, the central angle is $\Delta\varphi_k$ we replace it with a circular sector.

The face of such a circular sector $\Delta S_k = \frac{1}{2} r^2(\theta_k) \Delta\varphi_k$ is calculated by the formula.

The face S of the curved sector OAB can be considered as the face of a figure composed of n circular partial sectors:

$$S \approx \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta S_k = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{2} r^2(\theta_k) \Delta\varphi_k \tag{19}$$

(19) the approximate equality $[\varphi_{k-1}; \varphi_k]$ is more accurate the smaller the cross-sections are. The right-hand side of (19) is an integral sum for a continuous function.

4. We accept the limit value of the integral sum as the surface $\lambda = \max_{[\alpha; \beta]} \Delta\varphi_k \rightarrow 0$ of the curved sector OAB :

$$S = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n r^2(\theta_k) \Delta\varphi_k = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} r^2(\varphi) d\varphi$$

Thus, the face of the curved sector is calculated by the following formula.

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} r^2(\varphi) d\varphi$$

In general, as x changes, the cross-sectional area S changes, that is, it is a function of the variable x . We denote it by $S(x)$. We consider the function $S(x)$ to be continuous on the section $[a, b]$, where a and b are the abscissas of the edge (boundary) sections of the given body T .

To calculate the volume V of the body T , we use the algorithm consisting of making an integral sum and moving to the limit.

1. We divide the section $[a, b]$ into $a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_{n-1} < x_n = b$ n sections using points .

$\Delta x_k = x_k - x_{k-1}$, $\lambda = \max_{[a;b]} \Delta x_k$, $k = \overline{1, n}$ we enter the designations. Split points x_k We pass planes perpendicular to $x = x_k$ $k = \overline{1, n}$ the Ax axis through . a family of planes T divides the body into layers each of thickness Δx_k $k = \overline{1, n}$

2. Each $[x_{k-1}; x_k]$, $k = \overline{1, n}$ part is arbitrarily ξ_k from the section we choose a point and calculate the value of the function $S(x)$ at this point $S(\xi_k)$.

3. $[x_{k-1}; x_k]$ We assume that the function $S=S(x)$ is invariant and has a value of $S(\xi_k)$ Then, in each layer of the body T , the base $S(\xi_k)$ and the generator can be parallel to the axis Ox . This part is a straight cylinder

height Δx_k , the volume $\Delta V_k = S(\xi_k)\Delta x_k$ is calculated by the formula.

The volume of the body V is approximately equal to the volume of the figure consisting of cylinders with n steps:

$$V \approx \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta V_k = \sum_{k=1}^n S(\xi_k)\Delta x_k$$

Obviously, $\lambda = \max_{[a;b]} \Delta x_k$ the smaller it is, the more accurate the approximation is.

We accept deb as the value of the required volume $V = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=1}^n S(\xi_k) \Delta x_k$

Since the expression under the limit $[a, b]$ is the integral sum of the function $S(x)$ which is continuous on the section $[a, b]$

$$V = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \sum_{k=1}^n S(\xi_k) \Delta x_k = \int_b^a S(x) dx$$

Thus, the volume of the body located between the planes $x=a$ and $x=b$, if the cross-sectional surface perpendicular to the axis $S = S(x)$, $x \in [a; b]$ Ox is a known function,

$$V = \int_b^a S(x) dx \quad (21)$$

determined by the formula.

An example . $\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1$ Calculate the volume of the body bounded by the ellipsoid.

Solving . If we intersect the ellipsoid with $\frac{y^2}{b^2(1-\frac{h^2}{a^2})} + \frac{z^2}{c^2(1-\frac{h^2}{a^2})} = 1$ the $x=h$ plane, an ellipse

is formed in the section. The semi-axes of this ellipse $b\sqrt{1-\frac{h^2}{a^2}}$ are and , and the surface $S =$

$S(h) = \pi bc(1 - \frac{h^2}{a^2})$ is $c\sqrt{1 - \frac{h^2}{a^2}}$ equal to . (21) is the desired volume according to the formula

$$V = \int_{-a}^a S(h) dh = \int_{-a}^a \pi bc \left(1 - \frac{h^2}{a^2}\right) dh = \pi bc \left(1 - \frac{h^3}{3a^2}\right) \Big|_{-a}^a = \frac{4}{3} \pi abc.$$

In particular, when $a=b=c=r$, a sphere with radius r is formed and its volume $\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3$ is

An example . $\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$ calculate the volume of the body formed by rotating the ellipse around the Ox axis.

Solving . (22) according to the formula

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \int_{-a}^a \pi y^2 dx = \int_{-a}^a \frac{\pi b^2}{a^2} (a^2 - x^2) dx = \frac{\pi b^2}{a^2} \left(a^2 x - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-a}^a = \\ &= 2\pi \frac{b^2}{a^2} \left(a^3 - \frac{a^3}{3} \right) = \frac{4}{3} \pi ab^2. \end{aligned}$$

Summary. While writing this course work " Applications of definite integral to geometrical

problems ", I first prepared literature and sources related to this topic. I got acquainted with the information on the subject of the integral concept, learned information on the subject that I did not know before and strengthened my knowledge. My prepared coursework consists of introduction, main part, conclusion and used literature.

For the article, I reviewed the literature in various ways. Among them, I used more of the knowledge written by the teachers who were teaching us. I also read foreign literature. There is a book in them that surprised me a lot. God willing, I would have studied English and worked on that book.

In the subject of mathematical analysis, we mainly studied elementary mathematics. In this series, we studied two different integrals. But even within them, many integrals are divided into different sections. I learned that in this course work.

I thought to myself, why is this topic given to us? It leads to further improvement of the knowledge we have received in the subject . He thought that the topic of my article was difficult. But the teachers helped. I am grateful to them.

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